

Speculation on Quantum Interference

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. Sept. 27, 2025

In a previous note, we suggested that one may introduce the notion of probability into a Newtonian two-body collision (which automatically conserves probability). We argued first, that unlike an ideal gas, for which $p(e_i)$ is real because one may have different numbers of particles with energy e_i , in a two body collision, one has a single particle with p_1 (vector) and another with p_2 . A real valued probability seems to make no sense. This suggests a complex value probability with a modulus of 1, e.g. $\exp(i p \text{ constant})$ for each dimension (i.e. p_x, p_y, p_z). Then, $\exp(i p_1 C) \exp(i p_2 C) = \exp(i (p_1+p_2) C)$ and one may argue that one must have the same probability after the collision, so any $(\exp(i (p_3+p_4)))$ suffices with the same weight as long as $p_1+p_2=p_3+p_4$ (vectors). The problem, as shown in previous notes, is that $\exp(ipC) \neq \exp(-ipC)$. As a result, we suggested using $\exp(i p x)$ (here $p=p(x)$).

It seems that one must now interpret $\exp(i p x)$. It represents a free particle and so may be used to show conservation of momentum, with x disappearing if one uses: $\exp(-ip_3x) \exp(-ip_4x) \exp(ip_1x) \exp(ip_2x)$ ((1)). A fundamental point, however, is that $\exp(ipx)$ implies that p (as delivering an impulse) has probability values for different x values which means it may interact with one or the other slit of a two slit apparatus, something that does not happen in classical physics. This multi- x range of probability, however, only occurs when there is an interaction, i.e. the 2-slit apparatus must exist. When one does not measure such spatially separated possible interactions (slits), as in ((1)), then x does not appear. (We discuss this in more detail.) Likewise, $\exp(-ipx) \exp(ipx)$ eliminates x as well because there is no interaction.

If, however, an interaction does occur, as in a two-slit experiment or bound state with potential $V(x)$, then one must consider probabilities for interactions at different x points and the form $\exp(-ip_1x) \exp(ip_2x)$ is not 0, but only becomes 0 upon integration of x . In other words, with interactions present, one cannot predict a particle trajectory and interaction point and so one cannot argue that $\exp(-ip_1x) \exp(ip_2x) = 0$ at a point x because one has a particle which may be (in theory) at one point, but then interact at one slit point or another. Thus, the idea of conservation of momentum appears upon integrating over x and not a point in this case. We suggest that it is the possibility of $\exp(ipx)$ representing an interaction at one point or another which allows one to consider $\exp(-ip_2x) \exp(ip_1x)$, whereas in Newtonian mechanics trajectory and interaction point are predictable and one could not mix different momenta, p_1, p_2 , as this would violate conservation of momentum. In the case of ((1)), $\exp(ip_1x) \exp(ip_2x)$ has the form of a free particle and so it is as if one has no interaction, while $\exp(ip_1x) + \exp(ip_2x)$ must represent an interaction.

Probability As Emerging From Newtonian Mechanics

We have argued in a previous note that one may introduce probability into an elastic Newtonian two body scattering problem, if one argues that given e_1, e_2 and p_1, p_2 (vectors), one has no preference for the outcome e_i, e_j and p_3, p_4 as long as:

$$e_1 + e_2 = e_i + e_j \quad ((2a)) \quad \text{and} \quad p_1 + p_2 = p_3 + p_4 \quad ((2b))$$

In the case of one dimension, this seems to imply that:

$$P(p) = \exp(i p C) , \text{ where } C \text{ is a constant and } p \text{ is the momentum } ((3))$$

We use a complex probability with modulus 1 because all free particles have the same real weight unlike $p(e_i)$ in a Maxwell-Boltzmann gas.

The problem with ((3)) (as noted in previous notes) is that $\exp(i p C) \neq \exp(-ipC)$ which is a problem. We thus suggested:

$$P(p,x) = \exp(i p x) ((4)) \text{ (one dimension)}$$

(Similarly, one has $\exp(-iEt)$)

((4)) leads to a major consequence, namely that there is probability for p to interact at different x points, and not the center-of-mass point as in classical physics. If this is the case, one has a probability for a particle to interact with one or the other slit of a 2-slit apparatus if the slit spacing is about \hbar/p . Interactions do not occur at the deterministic center-of-mass point like in classical physics. We suggest that the key word here is “interactions” because if there are no probabilistic interactions (different x points), one must have the results of Newtonian mechanics, while if there are different x point interaction probabilities, one may have an expression which seems to violate conservation of momentum at a point x , but not over a range (integral over dx). We wish to examine this idea explicitly.

Conservation of Momentum in a 2-Body Collision

Even in quantum mechanics, there is conservation of momentum in a 2-body collision. One might argue that a 2-body collision is certainly an interaction, but it is treated as if one has certain total momentum before (i.e. a free particle with this momentum created by the product $\exp(ip_1x)\exp(ip_2x)$), and another free particle (product $\exp(ip_3x)\exp(ip_4x)$ afterwards. Thus, one does not focus on a probability of interaction at different x points. As a result, for total conservation of momentum, one may introduce:

$$\exp(-ip_3x)\exp(-ip_4x) \exp(ip_1x)\exp(ip_2x) = 1 ((5))$$

In this manner, x disappears because one does not deal with the non-Newtonian probability to interact at different x points and simply wishes to show conservation of overall momentum.

Single Free Particle

Given ((5)), if one has a single free particle, it also does not interact with probabilities for an interaction at x_1 and another at x_2 (as there is no 2-slit mechanism etc). One may write, from ((5))

$$\exp(-ipx) \exp(ipx) = 1 \quad ((6))$$

((6)) removes the effect of interference with a 2-slit apparatus etc because one is not considering any such spatially probabilistic interaction. One should obtain a Newtonian or classical result. We suggest that ((6)) is linked to the usual Newtonian spatial density:

$$P(x) = dx/\sqrt{L} \text{ where } L \text{ is a length } ((7))$$

In other words, one removes the “information” about probabilities for possible interactions at different x values, because if one really only has a free particle (represented by $\exp(ipx)$), then there are no interactions and no quantum effects. Mathematically, to manifest this, one must use ((6)) which follows from ((5)) which represents conservation of momentum, we argue.

The Case of a Probabilistic Spatial Interaction

One may now consider cases in which there is a clear probability for interactions at different points in space. Two examples include a 2-slit apparatus and bound state with potential $V(x)$. In the case of a probability for an interaction at two different x points, one must include “after-interaction” results for the two or more x points. In the 2-slit case, this means that a particle may interact with one slit or the other. Given that $\exp(ipx)$ is a probability, one must use an OR (plus) approach:

$$\exp(i p \cdot r_1) + \exp(i p \cdot r_2) \quad ((8))$$

Here it is assumed that the magnitude $|p|$ of the original momentum is not changed, only its angle. R_1 is a vector from the center of slit 1 to a point on a screen, and r_2 a vector from the center of slit 2 to the same point.

In the case of a potential, $\exp(ipx)$ interacts with $V(x)$ to create a set of $\exp(i p_j x)$'s and so one has:

$$W(x) = \text{Sum over } p \ a(p)\exp(ipx) \quad ((9))$$

In classical mechanics, one cannot consider momentum violating situations at a point, but in the quantum interaction at different x points case, one may consider momentum violation at a point. It just cannot be violated when one integrates over x . Thus, one may write:

$$(\exp(i p \cdot r_1) + \exp(i p \cdot r_2)) \cdot (\exp(i p \cdot r_1) + \exp(i p \cdot r_2)) \quad ((10))$$

$$\text{and } W^*(x)W(x) \quad ((10))$$

One may see from ((10)) that one has terms such as:

$$\exp(-i p_1 x) \exp(i p_2 x) \quad ((11))$$

Classically, these would be forbidden as they violate momentum conservation at a point, but $\exp(ipx)$ has the probability to interact at different points and so one does not know at which point it interacts with certainty. Thus, ((10)) is fine, but when one integrates:

$$\int dx \exp(-ip_1x) \exp(ip_2x) = 0 \text{ if } p_1 \neq p_2 \text{ ((12))}$$

.As a result, the quantum spatial probability density is really one that is directly linked to the fact that there exists a probability for a particle to interact at different x points (apart from its center-of-mass point as in Newtonian mechanics) and this may involve violation of conservation at a point (because one cannot pinpoint a particle at a point), but not over an integral over x .

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that $\exp(ipx)$ emerges as a probability which is invariant under $p \rightarrow -p$, $x \rightarrow -x$ (one dimension) and indicates that any p_3, p_4 pair have the same probability as outcomes in a 2-body collision if $p_1 + p_2 = p_3 + p_4$. The problem is that one now has the presence of the variable x . $\exp(ipx)$ indicates that one has a probability to interact at different x points (i.e. not at the given center-of-mass one of Newtonian mechanics). Thus, a particle might interact with one slit or the other in a 2-slit apparatus with slit separation of about \hbar/p .

This brings one to the question: What if there is no interaction specifically involving different possible x interaction points? For example, if one only wishes to demonstrate conservation of momentum, then one may use $\exp(ipx)$ in such a way that x disappears, i.e.

$$\exp(-ip_3x) \exp(-ip_4x) \exp(ip_1x) \exp(ip_2x) = 1 \text{ if } p_1 + p_2 = p_3 + p_4$$

From this, one may apply $\exp(-ip_1x) \exp(ip_1x)$ to a single free particle.

Again, this means that one does not focus on any probability to have interactions at different x points. Thus, 1 is a classical result meaning that the particle may be at any x point with the same probability.

There are cases, however, for which one must consider a probability for interactions at different x points. Two examples are the 2-slit apparatus and a bound state with potential $V(x)$. In the bound state case, one has different p values created and so has an OR situation categorized by $W(x) = \sum_p a(p) \exp(ipx)$. Writing $W^*(x)W(x)$ shows one may have cross terms $\exp(-ip_1x) \exp(ip_2x)$ which suggest violation of conservation of momentum at a point (p_1 versus p_2), but one cannot place the interaction of a particle at a point in such a case and so one is only interested in the integral over x . Thus, the quantum spatial density $W^*(x)W(x)$ seems to be one that is created by considering probabilities for interactions at different x points and this may violate conservation of momentum at an x point (but one cannot pinpoint a particle's interaction at a point and so this is not an issue), but not on average, we argue.